

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CREATIVE RESEARCH THOUGHTS (IJCRT)

An International Open Access, Peer-reviewed, Refereed Journal

A STUDY ON THE SELECTED ANTHROPOMETRIC MEASUREMENTS ASSOCIATION WITH PERFORMANCE OF KABADDI PLAYERS.

^{1*}G.Venkateswara Rao, Research Scholar, Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh, India.

^{2**}Dr.B. Gowri Naidu, Government Medical College, Andhra Pradesh, India.

^{3***}Prof. N. Vijay Mohan, Andhra University, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was relationship among anthropometric measurements and Kabaddi player's performance. The 82 male Kabaddi players were selected from National level representation in Andhra Pradesh on non-randomly by purposive sample was used. Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation was used to Analysis of the collected data on anthropometric measurements are Height (0.585*), Sitting Height (0.259*), Weight (0.364*), Palm Span (0.239*), upper Arm Length (0.462*),Forearm length (0.299*), Hand Length (0.379*), Upper Leg Length (0.627*), Lower leg length (0.389*),Chest Circumference (0.397*), Wrist Circumference (0.473*), Thigh Circumference (0.313*), Calf Circumference (0.271*), Shoulder Diameter (0.573*), Upper Arm Diameter (0.251*) and BMI (0.271*) coefficient of correlation with Kabaddi players performance had been positively with significant level 0.05. Remaining anthropometric measurements not correlated on this current study.

Key words: Anthropometric, Measurements, Kabaddi, Performance.

Introduction

Kabaddi is a combative team game. It combines Defence and offence and is played with absolutely no equipment, in a 13 meters x 10 meters rectangular court, either it may be outdoors or indoors with seven players on each side of the ground. Each side takes alternate chances for offence and defense. The basic idea of the game is to score points by entering into opponents' court and touching as many defense players as possible without getting caught in a single breath". (H.V.Nataraj 2008) There are basically two special of skills in Kabaddi i.e. Defence and offence. Kabaddi players, on the basis of their role in the game, can be divided to four groups namely Raiders, Corner, Coverer and All-rounders. The raiders are attackers, corner and coverer are defenders, whereas all-rounders perform both duties of attacking and defending. Kabaddi players of different playing positions performed different specified skill during the competitions which required a specified body shape and ability. Therefore, the custody of essential anthropometric variables

provides an edge to player to top performance his/her opponents. But we could not find any study on the anthropometrics parameters of Kabaddi players in relation to their playing positional performance.

In Kabaddi, anthropometry and motor performance ability of players seems to be the most vital determinants of success. Anthropometric measurements have the potential to quantify the relationship between bone mass, body structure, physical characteristics and individual players' sporting abilities thereby providing the basis for evaluating Kabaddi performance. Anthropometric measurements are often used to classify players according to their respective age or level of performance. Height is an advantage in executing attacking in the game of Kabaddi.

Anthropometric profiles of elite athletes provide insight into the requirements for competing at top level in particular sports. Previous reports have shown that body structure and morphological characteristics are important determinants of performance in many sports and certain physical impressions such as body composition (body fat, body mass, muscle mass) and physique (somatotype) can significantly influence athletic performance (Carter 1984). Children experiencing early success in a particular sport, not necessarily at a (high) competitive level, might increase their chances for sustained sports participation and an active lifestyle later on. With respect to talent identification, children with a profile that matches the requirements of a specific sport from a young age on will more likely continue training and by consequence have better chances on an optimal talent development pathway. Anthropometric means the scientific study of the measurements and proportion of the human body parts either living or non-living. Anthropometric measurements as an effective role with best performance Kabaddi players may to give as best as possible top form. The present study is anthropometric measurements with relation to Kabaddi player's performance. Its leads to may won the match.

Methodology

Purpose of the Study: This study would be decided to the anthropometric measurement's relation with Kabaddi player's performance.

Selection of the Subjects: The 82 male Kabaddi players were selected from National level representation in Andhra Pradesh on non-randomly by purposive sample was used.

Figure-I
Selected of the Anthropometric Measurements

S. No	Anthropometric Measurements	Equipment	Criterion Measures
1	Weight	Weighing Machine.	Kilograms
2	Height	Stadiometer	Centimeter
3	Sitting Height	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
4	Hand Length	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
5	Upper Arm Length	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
6	Fore Arm Length	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
7	Hand Breadth	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
8	Upper Leg Length	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
9	Lower Leg Length	Anthropometer Rod	Centimeter
10	Foot Length	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
11	Foot Breath	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
12	Chest Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
13	Upper Arm Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
14	Fore Arm Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
15	Wrist Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
16	Thigh Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
17	Calf Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
18	Ankle Circumference	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
19	Upper Arm Diameter	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
20	Elbow Diameter	Sliding Caliper	Centimeter
21	Shoulder Diameter	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
22	Hip Diameter	Flexible Tape	Centimeter
23	Ankle Diameter	Sliding Caliper	Centimeter
24	BMI	Calculation	Percentages

Collection of the Data and Tools

The data had been collected by administrating the standard procedures for taking anthropometric measurements as well as Kabaddi player's performance and tools had been used weighing machine for Weight, Stadiometer for Height and Flexible measuring tape for Lengths, Diameters and Circumference measurements. The score is recorded weights in kegs and remaining the nearest one tenth of the centimeters.

Statistical Analysis and Discussions

In order to find out the relationship of anthropometric measurements with Kabaddi performance with the Karl Pearson coefficient of correlation is used and testing the Hypothesis the level of confidence is 0.05.

Figure-II
Anthropometric Measurements Association with Kabaddi Playing Performance

S. No	Anthropometric Measurements	Coefficient of Correlation 'r'
1	Weight	0.364*
2	Height	0.585*
3	Sitting Height	0.259*
4	Hand Length	0.379*
5	Upper Arm Length	0.627*
6	Fore Arm Length	0.299*
7	Palm Span	0.239*
8	Upper Leg Length	0.462*
9	Lower Leg Length	0.389*
10	Foot Length	0.197
11	Foot Breath	0.189
12	Chest Circumference	0.397*
13	Upper Arm Circumference	0.201
14	Fore Arm Circumference	0.213
15	Wrist Circumference	0.473*
16	Thigh Circumference	0.313*
17	Calf Circumference	0.271*
18	Ankle Circumference	0.179
19	Upper Arm Diameter	0.251*
20	Elbow Diameter	0.203
21	Shoulder Diameter	0.573*
22	Hip Diameter	0.117
23	Ankle Diameter	0.113
24	BMI	0.271*

N=82, $r_{0.05(82)} = 0.217$, *Significant at 0.05 level.

An analysis of the above table indicates that Kabaddi performance is significantly related to measurements Height (0.585*), Sitting Height (0.259*), Weight (0.364*), Palm Span (0.239*), upper Arm Length (0.462*), Forearm length (0.299*), Hand Length (0.379*), upper Leg Length (0.627*), lower leg length (0.389*), Chest Circumference (0.397*), Wrist Circumference (0.473*), Thigh Circumference (0.313*), Calf Circumference (0.271*), Shoulder Diameter (0.573*), Upper Arm Diameter (0.251*) and BMI (0.271*) as obtained values of correlation were greater than the value of $r = 0.217$ the correlation to be significant at 0.05 level of confidence. The remaining anthropometric measurements as their correlation values are less than the value of $r = 0.217$ need for significance at 0.05 level of confidence.

Figure-III
Anthropometric Measurements and Kabaddi Players Performance

As for the results finally, the study reveals that Kabaddi performance ability is significantly related to measurements are Height (0.585*), Sitting Height (0.259*), Weight (0.364*), Palm Span (0.239*), upper Arm Length (0.462*), Forearm length (0.299*), Hand Length (0.379*), upper Leg Length (0.627*), lower leg length (0.389*) Chest Circumference (0.397*), Wrist Circumference (0.473*), Thigh Circumference (0.313*), Calf Circumference (0.271*), Shoulder Diameter (0.573*), Upper Arm Diameter (0.251*) and BMI (0.271*). As per the analysis, my suggestion to the coaches, physical directors, physical education teachers, physical instructors to concentrate on the above anthropometric measurements while selecting or screening for Kabaddi players in a basic level. It may be given effective and top performance in a specific competition.

Reference

1. Borrow Harold M. and McGee Rosemary (1979), A Practical Approach to Movements in Physical Education. Philadelphia: Leaand Febiger.
2. Verma J. P. (2000), A text book on sports statistics, Venus publication, Gwalior. (M.P.).
3. Nelson N. P. and Johnson C. R. (1970), Measurement and Statistics in Physical Education, Belmont, California, Wordsworth Publishing Company Inc.
4. Battaglia G, Paoli A, Bellafiore M, Bianco A, Palma A. Coll Antropol. (2014), Influence of a sport-specific training background on vertical jumping and throwing performance in young female basketball and players' Sports Med Phys Fitness.2014 Oct;54(5):581-7.
5. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2017. "Criterion anthropometric measurements with relation to fast bowler's performance". International Journal of Current Research, 09, (02), 46438-46440.
6. Belmont, California, Wordsworth Publishing Company Inc.
7. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2017. "Criterion anthropometric measurements with relation to fast bowler's performance". International Journal of Current Research, 09, (02), 46438-46440. AIBA. (2017).
8. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2017. "Training performance Physical Fitness Components Association with Hockey Playing" International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research, Volume 6, Issue 3(8), March 2017.

9. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2016. "Performance Physical Fitness Components as Predictors of Kho-Kho performance ability" Research Journal of Physical Education Sciences, Vol. 4(9), 1-3, November (2016).
10. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2017. "Criterion performance physical fitness components relation with Kabaddi playing ability" Research Journal of Physical Education Sciences, Vol. 5(2), 1-3, February (2017).
11. Gowri Naidu, B., 2016. "Relationship of selected performance physical fitness components to the performance of jumpers" International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health 2016; 3(6): 319-322.
12. Gowri Naidu, B. and Vijay Mohan, N., 2017. "A study of performance physical fitness components of runners, jumpers and throwers" International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health 2017; 4(2): 103-105.
13. Sandhya Rani, T. and Satish Varma, R., 2017. "Performance physical fitness components relation with Badminton players performance ability" International Journal of Health, Physical Education and Computer Science in Sports 2017; Volume No. 27, pp 435-436.
14. Gowri Naidu, B., 2018. "Effectiveness of Fast Bowlers Performance Relation with Specific Physical Fitness Variables" Asian Journal of Physical Education and Computer Science in Sports Volume No.19, No.1.pp1-3.
15. <https://www.topendsports.com/sport/kabaddi/anthropometry.htm>

